

THE ELECTRONIC MEDIA COVERAGE OF FEMALES IN THE BOKO HARAM TERRORISM BETWEEN 2009 AND 2019

Onyinye Chime, Ph.D research student, Lawrence Udeagbala, Ph.D, and Adam Okene Ahmed Ph.D, Professor, and Provost of the National Defence Collage, Abuja

Department of History and War Studies, Nigeria Defence Academy, Kaduna

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Abstract: *Over the decades, irrefutable events had proven the existence of female violent nonstate actors who perpetrated violent extremism with agency. Yet, in the electronic media coverage of Boko Haram terrorism from 2009 to 2019, female perpetrators were provided spaces of invincibility by the electronic media. Stereotypical mainstream narrative portrayed women predominantly as victims of the terrorism, thereby overlooking women who committed acts of violent extremism. Using the history method of research, this study interrogated how electronic media like the British Broadcasting Corporation, Cable News Network, Nigeria Television Authority, Al Jazeera and the Channels TV covered the violence. Primary data were gathered from official documents and oral interviews from journalists from the five media organisations, aid workers, repentant male and female Boko Haram combatants, government and military personnels who worked in the theatres of the conflict within the period under study. Secondary data were drawn from related academic literature and news reports. The study found that the news frames employed by these in the coverage of women were predominantly the humanitarian crises, and the women as victim's frames, which blindsided female perpetrators, providing them spaces of invincibility. The study further argued that socio-cultural restrictions, the interference of charity organisations in media narratives, international and domestic laws, and information restriction by the military were militating factors that enforced media stereotypes. It concluded that gender-centric profiling of perpetrators must be eliminated, gender expertise of frontline journalists must be enhanced, and gender-inclusive definitions of war crimes were necessary in international and domestic laws.*

Onyinye Chime, Ph.D research student, Lawrence Udeagbala, Ph.D, and Adam Okene Ahmed Ph.D, Professor, and Provost of the National Defence Collage, Abuja

INTRODUCTION

Strategic, complex, and robust roles played by females in terrorism organisations, are underreported in electronic media coverage. Their participation in violent extremism is yet to be fully acknowledged by the electronic media organisations reporting on terrorist activities. With the proliferation of asymmetric warfare, intra-state violent extremism continues to rise, seemingly in perpetuity, while combatants evolved from being male and military, to nonstate actors that included female terrorists. Globally, terrorist organisations such as the Baader-Meinhof Gang of Germany, Liberation Tigers of Tamil Eelam (LTTE), Islamic State Iraq and Syria (ISIS), and Al Qaeda affiliates like *Harakat al-Shabaab al-Mujahideen*, enabled females' participation in terrorism. And in Nigeria, *Jama'atu Ahlis-Sunna Ladda'awati Wal-Jihad* (JAS) also known as Boko Haram, lent its platform to females violent nonstate actors.

In the Boko Haram organisation in Nigeria between 2009 and 2019, young women and girls provided logistical support, were recruiters,

propagandists, intelligence gatherers, weapons smugglers, suicide bombers and combatants. As violent nonstate actors, they attacked non-combatant civilians or used them as human shields. Still, the media maintained mainstream stereotypical narratives that silenced the vices of female perpetrators, while amplifying female victimhood in conformity to gender identity, gender norms and gender roles. These were in spite of historic accounts on female perpetrations of terrorism dating back to World War II,¹ and in more recent decades, to the 1994 Rwanda genocide,² the second Liberian Civil Wars,³ and the Sierra Leone Civil War.⁴ In those wars women engaged in the hard crimes of terrorism as serial killers, sex offenders, suicide bombers and torture of civilians.

The skewed media representations of females in Boko Haram terrorism remain the subject of debate for academics. One school of thought posits that media contents depicting women did not “acknowledge their several complex roles.”⁵ They further opined that women were featured primarily “from the perspective of victims” in terrorism reports that were “largely male-dominated.”⁶

¹ Jasenka Ferizović, “The Case of Female Perpetrators of International Crimes: Exploratory Insights and New Research Directions,” *European Journal of International Law* 31, no. 2, (September 2020): 455–488. <https://doi.org/10.1093/ejil/chaa037>.

² Sara E. Brown, “Female Perpetrators of the Rwandan Genocide,” *International Feminist Journal of Politics* 16, no. 3, (July 2014): 448-469. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14616742.2013.788806>.

³ Amnesty International, *Lessons from Liberia: Reintegrating Women in Post-Conflict Liberia*, (London: Amnesty International, 2009), 1. <https://www.amnesty.org/en/wp-content/uploads/2021/07/afr340022009en.pdf>.

⁴ Dara Kay Cohen, “Female Combatants and the Perpetration of Violence: Wartime Rape in the Sierra Leone Civil War,” *World Politics* 65, no. 3, (July 2013): 383 – 415. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0043887113000105>.

⁵ African Union Commission and UN Women, *Handbook for Reporters on Women, Peace and Security*, 2.

⁶ UN Women, *Guidelines for Gender and Conflict-sensitive Reporting* (Geneva: UN Women, 2019), 9.

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Employing qualitative research design based on the History method, primary data were gathered from oral interviews with relevant personae, and secondary data drawn from pertinent academic literature. This article interrogated the coverage of women on electronic media such as the BBC, Al Jazeera, CNN, Channels Television and NTA, through the following questions: a) what practical difficulties encountered by frontline journalists in covering females within the theatres of the conflict, enforced gender stereotypes? b) What kind of journalism did the British Broadcasting Corporation (BBC), Cable News Network (CNN), Channels Television, Nigeria Television Authority (NTA), and Al Jazeera, employ in the news coverage of the Boko Haram terrorism? And c) How has the underrepresentation of females impacted gender-responsive reporting of Boko Haram terrorism?

Background on Women in Boko Haram Terrorism

Knowledge on the internal structures of the *Jama'atu Ahlis-Sunna Ladda'awati Wal-Jihad* in relation to females were limited, and the depth of their involvement unclear. A universal assumption was that female members were passivists coerced into violent extremism.

Founded in 2002 by Muhammed Yusuf, the sect metamorphosed from a radical Salafist movement to a Salafist-Jihadist group in 2009.⁷ The 2009 Boko Haram Uprising marked a tectonic shift in its modus operandi from critiquing the government, to blatant disregard for law and order, and later assassinations and suicide bombings. The extrajudicial killing of Muhammed Yusuf in police custody⁸ led to the emergence of his successor, Abubakar Shekau. Under Shekau's leadership, Boko Haram became the deadliest terrorist organisation in Nigeria and in the Lake Chad region.⁹ In 2014, the group feminised its terrorism by using young women and girls as tactical tools in the terrorism. Female suicide bombers were just one of the ways it used women.¹⁰ They assumed the roles of intelligence gatherers, recruiters, combatants, and propagandists. In the subsequent years, women began operating in hierarchies, held positions of power and executed agency.

The Militarised Females in Boko Haram

The females within the Boko Haram organisation were classified into groups that clearly defined their social status within the sect. They ranged from the *Bayi*, and *Awa'mi*, who were subjugated to a life of domestic servitude,

⁷ James Adewunmi Falode, "The Nature of Nigeria's Boko Haram War 2010-2015: A Strategic Analysis," *Perspectives on Terrorism* 10, no. 1, (February 2016): 41.

⁸ Emmanuel M. Ome and Ani Casimir, "Re-Examining Religious Insecurity in the Africa State: The Menace and Security Challenges of Boko Haram in Nigeria," *Open Journal of Political Science* 5, no. 2, (March 2015): 98. <http://dx.doi.org/10.4236/ojps.2015.52011>.

⁹ Adam Okene Ahmed, "Boko Haram Since 2009: A Study in Security History." 7th Professorial Inaugural Lecture Series. Nigerian Defence Academy (n.d.), 33. <https://www.academia.edu/37604598/>.

¹⁰ Farouk Chothia, "Boko Haram Crisis: Nigeria's female bombers strike," *BBC*, 6 August 2014, <https://www.bbc.com/news/world-africa-28657085>.

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to the *Amira*, *Ma'askar*, *Amaliyya*, *Rigalu'arm*, and *Hisbah*, who were elite groups of militarised women with varied degrees of power and privileges.

The *Bayi* or slaves and the *Awa'mi* (meaning the public) were at the bottom of the social ladder. While the *Bayi* were subjected to domestic servitude and sexual slavery,¹¹ the *Awa'mi*, or locals whose communities fell under the control of the jihadists, were subjugated to serve as farmers and informants.¹² However, it was the militarised women that played more complex, yet understated roles in the group. The *Amira*, *Ma'askar*, *Amaliyya*, *Rigalu'arm*, and *Hisbah* held prestigious positions designated to men, and had capacity to engage the Nigeria military in combat.¹³ They were ideologues who saw nothing wrong in the extrajudicial killings of other women. Acts of amputating and slaughtering of perceived offenders were considered “the work of Allah,” and were often executed without guilt.¹⁴ Their roles were distinct with definite responsibilities.

Amiras were women leaders in charge of different facets of women's activities. An *Amiran Yaki* is a female commander in charge of war, *Amiran Mata* a female commander in charge of the women), *Amiran Gazuwa*, female

commander in charge of bombers and *Amiran Mustadafin* was in charge of widows and divorcees, amongst others. They made life or death decisions such as determined which girl became a suicide bomber, amputate women for stealing or behead them on allegations of witchcraft or adultery.¹⁵ Testaments by former members inferred how *Amiras* defended barracks from military invasions by summoning all the women to battle in defence of the territory.¹⁶ In such circumstance, she also had ability to order soldiers under her husband's command for the said purpose.

Still, it would be an inaccurate claim to say all *Amiras* embraced the powers their status availed them. There were women leaders who opted not to exercise these powers, and even others who went further to openly criticise the excessive corporal punishments and extrajudicial executions, which all the women interviewed for this study, acknowledged were prevalent in the *Daulla* or Boko Haram's self-designated territories.¹⁷ In this policed society, some female commanders found ways to opt out of executing their powers while fulfilling their primary assignments. For instance, during the research interview, an *Amiran gazuwa* shared how she strategically restricted her powers by

¹¹ Interview with Baba Gas, 46, Boko Haram senior commander *Kayt*, Mubi, 13-09-24.

¹² Interview with Fatima Suleiman, 20, Boko Haram *Amiran Yaki*, Mubi, 12-09-24.

¹³ Interview with Abbati Malan Fari, 22, Boko Haram senior commander *Naqip*, Mubi, 13-09-24.

¹⁴ Interview with Adamu Rugurugu, 57, *Kayt*, *Naqip*, *Munzur* Boko Haram commander in charge of Gwoza under Abubakar Shekau, Maiduguri, 17-02-

24; Interview with Gambo Usman, 26, Boko Haram *Amira Gazuwa*, Mubi, 12-09-24.

¹⁵ Interview with Samira Garba, 25, Boko Haram *Amira Gazuwa*, Maiduguri, 17-02-24; Interview with Adamu Rugurugu, 57.

¹⁶ Interview with Ja'afar Lala, 32, Boko Haram senior commander *Munzur*, Mubi, 12-09-24.

¹⁷ Interview with Maryam Abdullahi, 24, Boko Haram *Amira Mata*, Maiduguri, 18-02-24.

limiting the number of persons under her command to two young children.¹⁸ Even though she was not overtly dissident, she admitted that she made concerted efforts to ensure there were no deaths weighing on her conscience.

The *Ma'askar* is a female military wing of Boko Haram and consisted of intelligence officers and combatants. They gathered information, made arrests, but were not empowered to execute punishment. They were extensively trained in the use of firearms such as rocket-propelled grenades (RPG), and magnetic accelerated cannon (MAC).¹⁹ Typically, a *ma'askar* was on a 24hours call, ready for mobilisation when necessary. Aptly describing this role, Abbati Malan Fari, a repentant *Naqip* who fought under Shekau, opined that, for a *ma'askar*, going to war was as mandatory as life itself.²⁰ Nonetheless, these women did not necessarily participate in all the battles, particularly the long-drawn ones. Their tactical values as women were best brought to bear in operations that had in the past proved difficult to win for male combatants.²¹ This was because the women were perceived as braver and more resilient than the men.²²

Rijalu'arm in Islam referred to men in positions of authority such as prominent scholars. Within the Boko Haram organisation certain women

were elevated to this position. Female *rijalu'arm* enforced the law and its members were drawn from the *ma'askar* warriors. Although their identities as part of the *ma'askar* inferred their primary mandate was to battle with state actors, this select-group had an additional injunction of law enforcement. Within the civilian population in the *daulla*, difficult civil disobedience case were transferred to the *Rijalu'arm*. They enforced decorum on dissidents and outlaws.

Amaliyya, means to demonstrate faith through action in Arabic. It was the name for the female suicide bombing unit of Boko Haram. These female suicide bombers were primarily volunteers from amongst the women.²³ Indices for the determination of a would-be *amaliyya* included character, intelligence and faith.²⁴ A volunteer may be as young as 10 years old.²⁵ This did not infer that all female suicide bombers volunteered to die for the ideology. Indeed, claims that they were volunteers remained in contention, as there were women in this mix with intents grossly unrelated to ideological convictions. Investigations suggested that in a highly policed community such as Boko Haram's, it was not uncommon for an *Amaliyya* to volunteer solely for the purpose of exiting the organisation. This was regarded as an opportunity for disassociation, dead or alive.²⁶

¹⁸ Interview with Aisha Ibrahim, 18, Boko Haram *Amira Gazuwa*, Mubi, 12-09-24.

¹⁹ Interview with Aisha Hamman, 16, Boko Haram *Amira and Rijalu'am*, Mubi, 12-09-24.

²⁰ Interview with Abbati Malan Fari, 22...

²¹ Interview with Ja'afar Lala, 32...

²² Interview with Ja'afar Lala, 32...

²³ Interview with Gambo Usman, 26...

²⁴ Interview with Ja'afar Lala, 32...

²⁵ Interview with Ibrahim Ali, 28...

²⁶ Interview with Ibrahim Ali, 28...

Accounts drawn from interviews with female suicide bombers revealed intense motivations such as the prospect to depart from long suffering,²⁷ or the yearning to return to family.²⁸ Furthermore, there were accounts of coercions into becoming a suicide bomber. It was not uncommon for husbands to force their wives to volunteer as an *Amaliyya*, as punishment for domestic altercation.²⁹ Also, the participation of ten and under ten year olds in a profound enterprise as suicide bombing, raised empirical questions on the mental and intellectual capacity of the minors involved. Whatever might have informed their decisions, *Amaliyyas* were the most revered arm in the group. They were seen as an epitome of what the religious ideology aimed to be.

Hisbah, an Arabic term that refers to acts performed for the common good,³⁰ are a group that calls “to all that is good... forbidding what is wrong.”³¹ Within the *Daulla*, Boko Haram attributed this term to policing. This role was predominantly assigned to men, but women within the sect, who were perceived to have strong character and learning were elevated to this position.³² Female *hisbah* were more or less regarded as men.³³ They policed women and wielded such powers over them, that the

husbands had no right to intervene.³⁴ They conducted census and censorship on women, ensuring compliance to religious studies and social norms, arrested, detained, investigated, and executed sentences including flogging and the slaughter of offenders.³⁵ Although they oversaw the implementation of capital punishment, they were not necessarily under compulsion to carry out executions. Any woman with ability to do so, could volunteer to be an executioner, a function which was richly rewarded.³⁶ *Hisbah* were confined within the *daulla*, and did not participate in outside military operations.³⁷

News Frames Employed by BBC, CNN, NTA, Channels TV and Al Jazeera in the Coverage of Boko Haram

In spite of their robust participations in the violent extremism, news on militarised women in Boko Haram never made it to the news. In fact, frequency of news reports on the females in Boko Haram intensified after the abduction of the Chibok schoolgirls in 2014. Prior to their kidnap, coverage of the terrorism on Al Jazeera, the BBC and the CNN were sparse and focused only on major deadly attacks. In the same instance, the two Nigerian media outfits, the NTA and Channels TV were consistent on the

²⁷ Interview with Zainab Ja’afar, 23...

²⁸ Interview with Fatima Suleiman, 20...

²⁹ Interview with Gambo Usman, 26...

³⁰ Human Rights Watch, “*Political Shari’a*”? *Human Rights and Islamic Law in Northern Nigeria*, A1609, (New York: HRW, 2004).

<http://www.hrw.org/sites/default/files/reports/nigeria0904.pdf>.

³¹ The Qur’an 2:256, (Translate by Abdullahi Yusuf Ali).

³² Interview with Baba Gas, 46...

³³ Interview with Ja’afar Lala, 32...

³⁴ Interview with Abbati Malan Fari, 22...

³⁵ Interview with Abba Isa, 30, Boko Haram senior commander *Munzur*, Mubi, 13-09-24.

³⁶ Interview with Abbati Malan Fari, 22...

³⁷ Interview with Abbati Malan Fari, 22...

frequency of the news coverage of the terrorism. However, after news of the abduction broke, The BBC, CNN, Channels TV, NTA and Al Jazeera reports became more robust. Instantly, the entire mediascape was awakened to its responsibility. They covered diverse aspects of the abduction stories, from protests and campaigns for their release, to the Nigerian government's dilemma on whether to negotiate with terrorists. News stories were humanised, and for the first time, victims of the terrorism had names and faces. Two dominant news frames featured in the coverage of women in the violent extremism: a) humanitarian crises; and b) women as victims, were herein broadly examined.

The Humanitarian Crises News Frames

Kinetic operations in the political violence were the primal focus of the media, and this reflected in the headlines. Over half of the total headlines published in the five broadcast outfits under study were reports on the attacks. At intervals there were news contents about impacts of the violence on the civilian population. At those times, the humanitarian crises news frame was used to portray the plights of men, women, boys and girls who were trapped in the conflicts, had lost their homes, were stripped of all their resources, had no food security, lacked adequate healthcare and safe water, had their human rights abused among others. But it should be

stated that such humanitarian stories rarely featured. On those rare occasions when they did, news on humanitarian crises were generalised. There were no clearcut coverage of women in relation to the sect's activities.³⁸ For instance, prior to April 2014 schoolgirls' kidnaps, the international media was insensitive to the gendered nature of the abductions. Despite the numerous threats from Abubakar Shekau to kidnap and enslave women and girls in retaliation for the arrests of wives and relatives of the sect's leadership, journalists failed to make the connections. They failed to recognise that, in line with those threats, the people abducted were for the most part women and girls. Cases of kidnaps were reported in isolation and rarely gendered. Inadvertently the massive kidnaps of women and girls went unnoticed while news headlines screamed about the abductions but buried the crucial part of the information, that females were being targeted. Again, humanitarian news was majorly based on reports by charity organisations and not independent investigative journalism that appraise situations. Thus, it was common to see headlines such as: "Human Rights Watch says government officials and troops are exploiting women and girls who escaped grip of armed group;"³⁹ "Amnesty accuses Nigerian troops of

³⁸ Interview with Junaid Bindawa, 65, Major General retired - General Officer Commanding 7th Division, Nigeria Army in Maiduguri Borno State, Kaduna, 23-09-24.

³⁹ *Al Jazeera*, "HRW: Boko Haram refugees in Nigeria raped by officials," 31 October 2016, <https://www.aljazeera.com/news/2016/10/31/hrw-boko-haram-refugees-in-nigeria-raped-by-officials>.

raping women rescued from Boko Haram;”⁴⁰ “An Islamist insurgency has kept about one million children out of school in Nigeria and three neighbouring states, the UN children's agency has said.”⁴¹ Beyond quotes and pressers credited to NGOs, the media made no further efforts to ascertain the authenticity or otherwise of such statements. It was essential to state at this point that, this argument did not deny the fact that some agents of the state exploited the vulnerabilities of the women under their care. There were unscrupulous soldiers who abused their authority and were in turn court marshalled and dismissed. Such cases though far in-between and hardly know to the public, made headlines: ‘Air Force Officer Dismissed for Raping 14-Year-Old IDP’⁴²

Sequel to the schoolgirls’ abduction, humanitarian conditions of Boko Haram abductees formed a second news frame. Contents on casualties and survivor tales became the holy grail for humanitarian contents.⁴³ Lived-experiences of ex-militants were not left out by all three foreign electronic media.⁴⁴ For instance current affairs feature contents such as “*Using football to tackle*

Nigeria’s Boko Haram,” brought to the audience the life of militants jailed inside one of Nigeria’s prisons.⁴⁵ On the contrary, NTA had its role spelt out and reported in accordance to the wishes of government. Channels had less considerations on reporting the humanitarian crises beyond pressers from aid groups.

To principally base critical humanitarian reports on press statements was problematic, not just due to the lack of authentication as mentioned in the above paragraphs, but because it called into question depth of coverage. What was the depth of the crises? For instance, in press statements, political leaders and NGOs gave generic information that reeled out statistics without breakdown on the number of people in need of aid. They did not state who needed what. They mentioned that reliefs were being provided but failed to state the nature of relief or what was lacking that needed to be provided. According to Unaegbu, journalists failed to go beyond the numbers, the political statements and kinetic actions to ask the tough questions.⁴⁶

Women as Victims of the Boko Haram Terrorism

⁴⁰ Bukola Adebayo, “Amnesty accuses Nigerian troops of raping women rescued from Boko Haram,” *Al Jazeera* (Doha), 24 May 2018, <https://edition.cnn.com/2018/05/24/africa/nigerian-army-amnesty-report-rape-intl/index.html>.

⁴¹ *BBC*, “Nigeria’s Boko Haram ‘forces one million out of school,’” 22 December 2015, <https://www.bbc.com/news/world-africa-35159024>.

⁴² Akinola Ajibola, “Air Force Officer Dismissed for Raping 14-Year-Old IDP,” *Channels Television* (Lagos), 2 April 2019, <https://www.channelstv.com/2019/04/02/air-force-officer-dismissed-for-raping-14-year-old-idp/>.

⁴³ *BBC*, “Surviving Nigeria's Boko Haram,” 7 January 2016, <https://www.bbc.com/news/world-africa-35241610>.

⁴⁴ Anne Soy, “How I almost became a Boko Haram suicide bomber,” *BBC* (London), 22 March 2016, <https://www.bbc.com/news/world-africa-35864054>.

⁴⁵ *BBC*, “Using football to tackle Nigeria's Boko Haram,” 11 September 2015, <https://www.bbc.com/news/world-africa-34126346>.

⁴⁶ Interview with Lilian Unaegbu, 42, Aid worker in Maiduguri, served with NGOs including Oxfam and UN Women, Abuja, 03-10-23.

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The women as victims news frame found a place on the BBC, CNN, Channels Television, Al Jazeera and the NTA, particularly stories of the kidnapped Chibok girls.⁴⁷ For the most part, women victim stories were fundamentally focused on the Chibok girls whom, according to the findings of this research, experienced better treatments from the jihadists unlike the other female captives. This was due to: one, their tactical value as bargaining chip with the Nigeria government.⁴⁸ And two, according to Abu Bilal, the world paid the most attention to them because they were considered as young girls with bright futures.⁴⁹ Still, there were proliferations of headlines such as: ‘Where are Nigeria’s missing girls? On the hunt for Boko Haram,’⁵⁰ ‘I fled Boko Haram and had to leave my son behind;’⁵¹ ‘CNN, Al Jazeera Lied About ‘Supposed’ Chibok Girls’ Escape – Badeh;’⁵² ‘Nigeria’s kidnapped girls sold into marriage.’⁵³ The news agencies featured women and girls who were victims of the terrorists while in captivity. Although they were mostly presented

as part of the news,⁵⁴ personal experiences of some of the girls were specially featured as current affairs contents. These personal accounts gave some insight into the lives of the women who lived within the jihadist territories as victims.⁵⁵ But, they underrepresented women who were raped and exploited by security agents, aid workers and other government officials; women without social skills forced into roles of breadwinners of families; existing economic inequalities that subjugated women; and female perpetrators and conspirators with agency. Journalists on the frontlines failed to aptly capture these existing dynamics with the news frame they had for women. Nonetheless, there were a handful of stories from the CNN and Al Jazeera on women perpetrators and conspirators. A CNN report told the story of three women who seemed to have exercised agency by secretly recruiting women for marriage to Boko Haram members. One such article was the 5 July 2014 publication, “Nigeria: Arrested women recruiting for Boko Haram,”⁵⁶ a

⁴⁷ Ratidzai Ndhlovu, “‘I was flogged daily:’ Rescued Boko Haram survivors share tales of horror,” *CNN* (Atlanta), 14 May 2015, <https://edition.cnn.com/2015/05/14/opinions/boko-haram-survivors-share-tales-of-horror/index.html>.

⁴⁸ Interview with Adamu Rugurugu, 57...

⁴⁹ Interview with Abu Bilal, 27, Boko Haram Senior commander *Kay’ t*, Maiduguri, 17-02-24.

⁵⁰ Arwa Damon, Brent Swails and Nick Thompson, “Where are Nigeria’s missing girls? On the hunt for Boko Haram,” *CNN* (London), 30 March 2015, <https://edition.cnn.com/2014/06/10/world/africa/boko-haram-hunt-arwa-damon/index.html>.

⁵¹ British Broadcasting Corporation, “I Fled Boko Haram and Had to Leave My Son Behind,” *Report*, 14 September 2019, <https://www.bbc.com/news/av/world-africa-49690154>.

⁵² Channels Television, “CNN, Al Jazeera Lied About ‘Supposed’ Chibok Girls’ Escape – Badeh,” *Report*, 8 October 2014, https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=_gkG9SCPG_g.

⁵³ *Al Jazeera*, “Nigeria’s kidnapped girls sold into marriage,” 1 May 2014, <https://www.aljazeera.com/news/2014/5/1/nigerias-kidnapped-girls-sold-into-marriage>.

⁵⁴ British Broadcasting Corporation, “Boko Haram ‘Burnt My Mother Alive Infront of Me’,” *Report*, 5 October 2014, <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=uVV6nfYOMmY>.

⁵⁵ *BBC*, “Chibok diaries: Chronicling a Boko Haram kidnapping,” 23 October 2017, <https://www.bbc.com/news/world-africa-41570252>.

⁵⁶ Radina Gigova, “Nigeria: Arrested women recruited for Boko Haram,” *CNN* (Atlanta), 5 July 2014, <https://edition.cnn.com/2014/07/04/world/africa/nigeria-women-suspected-boko-haram/index.html>.

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report that cited the Nigeria military spokesman as source. Still, in the absence of first-hand accounts from the three arrested women, it was difficult to ascertain whether these female recruiters truly had agency, or they were victims of coercion. Consequently, media coverage failed to engage with women in the political violence beyond this frame, to interrogate violent female actors, much less hold them to account.

In addition to the news frame, there were choices of words used in the reporting which impacted greatly on how the audience internalised and interpreted the information on the women presented to them. While some employed words that absolutely portrayed these females as victims, others used expressions that totally silenced their existence within the context of specific events. A case in point was a BBC 18 December 2014 headline “Boko Haram unrest: Nigerian militants ‘kidnapped 200 villagers.’”⁵⁷ This news piece reported that an abduction had occurred when the jihadists invaded Gumsiri village in Damboa local government area of Borno state. But it downplayed who the abductees were. In this case they were women and children. While it could be argued that this article attempted to humanise the incident by its acknowledgement that irrespective of gender, the victims were foremost humans, it downplayed the implications this event

particularly had on women and the girls. Accounts of the events that occurred on that day attested to about 200 women and children being rounded up and taken away in trucks before the village was set on fire.”⁵⁸

Added to the choice of words employed to suppress the gendered nature of the conflicts, another common trait of the underrepresentation manifested itself through the media enforcement of male dominance. Women were perpetually assigned roles of victims in the news and rarely functioned as resource persons, experts, representatives of women or a person in authority. The dominance of the male gender was infinite in the news contents broadcasted by the five media platforms. It was enforced through assigned roles, where men occupy the roles of resource person such as analysts, spokesmen, representatives of authorities but rarely presented as victims.

The Challenges in Electronic Media Coverage of Women in Boko Haram Terrorism

Militarised women and girls had status, exercised agency and earned more highly than their male counterparts for killing perceived transgressors.⁵⁹ Yet, a number of factors including socio-cultural restrictions, obstructions by international and domestic laws,

⁵⁷ BBC, “Boko Haram Unrest: Nigerian Militants ‘Kidnap 200 Villagers,’” 18 December 2014, <https://www.bbc.com/news/world-africa-30529178>.

⁵⁸ BBC HAUSA, “Boko Haram: An Sace Mata da Yara 200 a Borno,” 18 December 2014,

https://www.bbc.com/hausa/news/2014/12/141218_bokoharam_gumsiri_kidna pp.

⁵⁹ Interview with Maryam Isa, 21, lived in the *daulla* for 6 years, Maiduguri, 18-02-24.

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access and information restrictions by the military, financial considerations in news deployment, and the exploitation of the last two factors by nongovernmental organisations inhibited news coverage of their activities.

Access and Information Restrictions by the military

Impactful journalism stems from access to accurate and timely information. However, these were largely unavailable in the coverage of Boko Haram terrorism due to bottlenecks beyond the control of the reporters. Frontline journalists contended with the strategic need of the Nigerian government and its military to control media narratives. This was hinged at the time on the inference that certain media contents undermined national security and national interest. In the President Goodluck Jonathan administration, government coordinated media responses devoid of discordant voices by restricting journalists' access to news sources.⁶⁰ It established the National Information Centre that was designed to manage crises communications by synergising all agencies connected to the counterterrorism campaign.⁶¹ And the Nigeria military granted journalists access to the

frontlines only on the condition that their reports “reflect and conform to national interest.”⁶² A photojournalist who covered the conflicts described the period as a “very complicated” one for journalists due to “little access on all fronts. No access from the military and it was very dangerous on the ground.”⁶³

Although the military organised embeds for journalists to join troops in patrols, its professional loyalty clashed with the interests of both parties.⁶⁴ Embeds were “heavily framed, heavily channelled.”⁶⁵ Often, these embedded exercises ended in internally displaced persons (IDP) camps as journalists never made it to the frontlines.⁶⁶ As such, reports were skewed as journalists had neither firsthand knowledge of events, nor a clear understanding that came from speaking to all sides.

The Protection of Female Violent Nonstate Actors by International and Domestic Laws

In times of any forms of violent extremism, international laws categorised women as vulnerable people alongside children, the sick, the elderly and persons with disabilities. The Geneva Protocol of 1925, and the Geneva

⁶⁰ Interview with Mike Omeri, 60, Former Director of National Orientation Agency (NOA) between 2012-2016, Abuja, 10-08-23.

⁶¹ Interview with Mike Omeri, 60...

⁶² Abdulkareem Haruna, “Army chief gives condition for embedding journalists in military operations,” *Premium Time* (Lagos), 5 April 2020. <https://www.premiumtimesng.com/news/top-news/386102-army-chief-gives-condition-for-embedding-journalists-in-military-operations.html?tztc=1>.

⁶³ Interview with Benedict Kruzen, 44, Freelance journalist based in Maiduguri in the first decade of the conflicts; reported and provided support for diverse

international media organisations, including the BBC, phone interview, 22-04-23.

⁶⁴ Paul G. Buchanan, “Facilitated News as Controlled Information Flows: The Origins, Rationale and Dilemmas of “Embedded” Journalism,” *Pacific Journalism Review: Te Koako* 17, no. 1, (May 2011): 103. <https://doi.org/10.24135/pjr.v17i1.374>.

⁶⁵ Interview with Benedict Kruzen, 44...

⁶⁶ Interview with Mike Omeri, 60...

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Conventions of 1949,⁶⁷ Universal Declaration of Human Rights 1948,⁶⁸ the Declaration of the Rights of the Child 1959,⁶⁹ the International Covenant on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights 1966,⁷⁰ and the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights 1967,⁷¹ obligates all state signatories to protect women.

Nigeria as a signatory to these treaties is prohibited from subjecting females to persecution, torture, punitive measures, degrading treatments and violence. These laws were established on the premise that women and children were innocent, but not adult males. However in the face of Boko Haram's asymmetric warfare, these protection provisions proved disruptive for the Nigerian state. The laws failed to take into account the massive shift in war practices from male-dominated and states-focused security, to intrastate conflicts involving gendered violent nonstate actors. Acknowledging this shift meant females in Boko Haram terrorism had evolved to assume multiple identities. They can no longer be identified solely as civilian population, as they now also identify as combatants, sympathisers,

and mobilisers in certain situations. Therefore, as the bedrock for counterterrorism policies, international and domestic laws obstructed the incorporation of the gendered nature of terrorism.

The Interference of Nongovernmental Organisations in Media Narratives

Navigating through military information blockade to gather news contents meant journalists were not only reliant on government pressers, they were also overdependent on nongovernmental organisations (NGOs). Registered, unregistered, and even non-existing nongovernmental organisations operated within Boko Haram's theatres of conflict.⁷² Among them were groups with vested interests in the news narratives that enhanced the chances of attracting donors to their in their NGOs.⁷³ For the purpose of survival they engaged journalists to push out narratives that favoured their core interests in the violence.⁷⁴ Journalists interviewed in this study alluded to NGO influence on through the creation of issues-specific themes, which were required to solve specific problems.⁷⁵

⁶⁷ United Nations General Assembly, "Resolution adopted by the General Assembly 3318 (XXIX). Declaration on the Protection of Women and Children in Emergency and Armed Conflict," A/RES/29/3318 (New York: United Nations, 1974), 2. <http://www.un-documents.net/a29r3318.htm>.

⁶⁸ UNHCR, "Universal Declaration of Human Rights," ST/DPI (02)/U59 (New York: United Nations Department of Public Information, 1948), <https://www.ohchr.org/en/universal-declaration-of-human-rights>.

⁶⁹ UNHCR, "Declaration of the Rights of the Child," A/RES/14/1386 (New York: UN., 1959). <https://digitallibrary.un.org/record/195831?v=pdf>.

⁷⁰ UNHCR, "International Covenant on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights," A/RES/2200 (New York: UN., 1959), 27. <https://digitallibrary.un.org/record/195831?v=pdf>.

⁷¹ UN, "International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights," Treaty Series volume 999, number 14668 (New York: UN., 1966) 172. https://treaties.un.org/doc/Treaties/1976/03/19760323%2006-17%20AM/Ch_IV_04.pdf.

⁷² Interview with Mike Omeri, 60...

⁷³ Interview with Mike Omeri, 60...

⁷⁴ Interview with Sarkin Yaki Bello, 67, Major General retired - first coordinator Nigeria Counterinsurgency and Counterterrorism in the Office of the National Security Adviser (ONSA) from 2011-2014, Abuja, 10-08-23.

⁷⁵ Interviews with Benedict Kruzen, 44.; Emperor Simon, 39, Channels Television Journalist, Abuja, 22-01-23; Mayeni Jones, 35, BBC Africa Correspondent, Lagos, 15-01-23; Yvonne Ndege, 45, Al Jazeera Journalist,

Onyinye Chime, Ph.D research student, Lawrence Udeagbala, Ph.D, and Adam Okene Ahmed Ph.D, Professor, and Provost of the National Defence Collage, Abuja

Limitations to information access, short turnaround time, inadequate staff welfare and resources meant frontline journalists, particularly freelance and local reporters, often recourse to NGOs to gain access to otherwise hard-to-reach locations. This predisposed them to become hands-for-hire to NGOs willing to pay for their services, and provide them secured means of transportation.⁷⁶ Journalists who benefited in this way compromised their ability to tell truth to power.⁷⁷

Socio-cultural Restrictions in the Coverage of Women Terrorists

Socio-cultural constructs embodied in patriarchy reinforce gender norms that elevates male authority and subjugates women.⁷⁸ In north-east Nigeria, Islam as a custodian of patriarchy, ascribes distinct roles, socially constructed for the male gender and the female gender.⁷⁹ Furthermore, Boko Haram's brand of Islam between 2009 and 2019, imposed unsubstantiated extremist views.⁸⁰ These religious and traditional practices determined women's conducts and expressions in public spaces.

Hence, on the one hand, women were required not to have agency. They stayed out of public discussions, and refrained from expressing personal opinions. On the other hand, journalists as products of these cultural orientations were not immune to its influences. These unconscious biases coupled with low literacy level among the women in terms of formal education, posed a challenge for journalists who had to work with the population.⁸¹ Recounting her experience while she lived and worked in Maiduguri, a French freelance journalist, posited that, speaking to people who lacked capacity for self-expression was a challenge she had to deal with.⁸²

Generally, limited skills in self-expression made women shy away from the media, and when they spoke with the media, articulating their thoughts and ideas were challenging. The lack of self-expression also keyed into gender roles or socially accepted behaviour for women required a female to be gentle, nurturing, protective, a homemaker, and the representation of life. Data drawn from interviews revealed that, through this worldview, the media projected women in Boko Haram organisation as frail and vulnerable

phone interview, 19-01-23; Dogara Bitrus, 37, Channels Television Journalist, Maiduguri, 01-02-23.

⁷⁶ Interview with Lilian Unaegbu, 42...

⁷⁷ Interview with Lilian Unaegbu, 42...

⁷⁸ Franca Attah, "Gender, Religion and Patriarchy: A Sociological Analysis of Catholicism and Pentecostalism in Nigeria," *Advances in Social Sciences Research Journal* 4, no. 14 (July 2017): 158-160.

DoI:10.14738/assrj.414.3482.

⁷⁹ Mohammed Aamir Ali, "Key Concepts in Gender Studies: Patriarchy and Religion" (MA Gender Studies 1st Semester, Jamia Millia Islamia University, n.d.) 1-8, <https://www.academia.edu/45530613/>.

⁸⁰ Alexander Thurston, "Boko Haram from Salafism to Jihadism," in *Salafism in Nigeria: Islam, Preaching, and Politics*, 194-195. (Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2016). DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1017/CBO9781316661987.009>.

⁸¹ Emmanuel A. Isah, Suleman Yakubu, and Timothy T. Adeleke, "Socio-Cultural Factors and Access to University Education in North-East Region of Nigeria," *East African Journal of Educational Research and Policy* 15, no. 1, (June 2020): 58.

⁸² Interview with Benedict Kruzen, 44...

victims of the terrorism.⁸³ Thus keying into mainstream narratives that these women were placed in subservient positions without agency.

The Impact of the BBC, Al Jazeera, NTA, CNN and Channels TV Coverage on Female in Boko Haram Terrorism

Traditionally, the complex nature of women's roles in the Boko Haram violent extremism were ignored in the BBC, CNN, Al Jazeera, NTA and Channels Television's coverage of Boko Haram terrorism. As a result knowledge about the depth of their involvement in the jihadist movement was unknown. This was due to a distinct absence of a women-centric perspective on the violent nonstate actors, in works done by frontline journalists. Debates on the existence of female perpetrators with agency led to a *cul-de-sac* due to inadequate comprehension of the victim-perpetrator dichotomy, which obscured the extent of their involvement, the way they operated, their drives, motivations, and the consequences of their activities. Female Boko Haram jihadists played complex roles which were often not visible, and therefore not acknowledged. In the first instance, women were taught combat skills primarily to be able to protect themselves and the camp in case of attack. Over time however, they use their new skills to support their husbands in combat.

Thus, it was not enough to report on their victimhood and passivity, their free choice also had to be questioned; because, while the

electronic media's categorisation of victims were presented as a direct contrast to perpetrators, in real conflict situations, victims and perpetrators were rarely distinguishable. While the media was sympathetic to the victimisation of women premised on stereotypes that they were passive participants, kidnapped by male fighters during brutal raids on their villages or from the roadsides, and forcefully labelled fighter's wives, over time these forced wives became not only victims and witnesses of war violence, but also the perpetrators. Accounts from female and male interviewees revealed that there were women who regarded their participation in the battlefield as an escape from victimhood by becoming a perpetrator. Being in control of violence, gave them more security, dominance and empowerment, as well as a chance to escape if they so wished.

These women exercised merciless authority over subordinate abductees, partook in looting campaigns and direct combats. Firsthand accounts gathered from this research revealed some depth to their prowess and drive in the political violence. Senior Boko Haram commanders alluded to a certain mystique and resilience that surrounded the militarised females on the battlefields. They acknowledged that female combatants could be more ruthless and more efficient during battles than their male counterparts.

⁸³ Interview with Abu Bilal, 27...

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Indeed, these militarised Boko Haram women perpetrated acts that ran parallel to stipulated socio-cultural identities and roles assigned to women. They were ideologues, violent non state actors and supporters of violent extremism who perpetrated extreme violence, but benefited from the exemptions privileged them as females. In reporting news on them, the CNN, BBC, Channels Television, NTA and Al Jazeera, selected certain versions of realities over others. Through their choice of news frames, they decided the identity of the gender that ought to be the protagonists, and what issues ought to be discussed about them in the public domain.

Even in instances where the violent roles of the militarised women were recognised, they were still designated victims, and outrightly denied agency. Sources in authority interviewed for this study were intentional when they denied these women the title of perpetrators, thereby stripping them of agency. The insinuation that their actions were due to male manipulation was

Conclusion

In Nigeria, *Jama'atu Ahlis-Sunna Ladda'awati Wal-Jihad* (JAS) also known as Boko Haram, initiated an asymmetric warfare where women evolved from victims of violent extremism, to become combatants and enforcers of laws like the *amiras*, *hisbah*, *rijalu'arm*, *amaliyyas*, and *ma'askars*. Still, the electronic media coverage of the terrorism blindsided female perpetrators, while focusing predominantly on women victims. Therefore, using Channels Television, Al Jazeera,

a dominant position that held sway. Social expectations and biases gave rise to misconceptions of female passivity in the jihadi-inspired terrorism. It propelled a belief in the media, and in the Nigeria counterterrorism programmes, that females could not climb the hierarchy within the sect; and therefore, pose no direct risk of violence to the public. However, field data revealed that females rose through the ranks of the Boko Haram organisation to positions of authority. Evidence gathered revealed that *bayis* who were at the bottom of the social strata, elevated up the ladder to hold prestigious positions such as *amira*, *rajalu'arm*, *ma'askar*, *hisbah* or *amaliyya*.

Not acknowledging the existing hierarchy among Boko Haram women imposed limitations on understanding the levels or categories of their victimhood, their activities as empathisers, and why and how did the victims evolve to become perpetrators and conspirators.

CNN, NTA and the BBC as case studies, news frames used in reports related to women in the sect were examined, and the challenges their frontline journalists faced reporting Boko Haram terrorism between 2009 and 2019, interrogated. The study finds that military information blockade denied journalists access to firsthand accounts from the frontlines. Socio-cultural restrictions deterred them from getting access to information, and also predetermined that women in Boko Haram were passive participants lacking

Onyinye Chime, Ph.D research student, Lawrence Udeagbala, Ph.D, and Adam Okene Ahmed Ph.D, Professor, and Provost of the National Defence Collage, Abuja

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agency. NGOs interfering in news narratives was also a factor that posed challenge to journalists. These, the study found, were projected in the dominant news frames of humanitarian crises, and female victimhood, used in the coverage of the terrorism. Therefore, the study posits that understanding the depth of women's participation requires a paradigm shift in perception. It is essential to eliminate gender-centric profiling of perpetrators, and instead contextualise gender analysis. To effectively identify female perpetrators, gender expertise of frontline journalists needs to be enhanced through specialised training. And gender-inclusive definitions of war crimes are necessities in the face of asymmetric warfare such as the Boko Haram terrorism.

Onyinye Chime, Ph.D research student, Lawrence Udeagbala, Ph.D, and Adam Okene Ahmed Ph.D, Professor, and Provost of the National Defence Collage, Abuja

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Table 1: List of contributors in oral interviews

Name of contributors	Age	Title/Occupation	Place of interview	Date of interview
Abba Isa,	30	Boko Haram senior commander <i>Munzur</i>	Mubi	13-09-24
Abbati Malan Fari	22	Boko Haram senior commander <i>Naqip,</i>	Mubi	13-09-24
Abu Bilal	27	Boko Haram Senior commander Kay't	Maiduguri	15-03-24
Adamu Rugurugu	57	<i>Kayt, Naqip, Munzur</i> commander in charge of Gwoza under Abubakar Shekau	Maiduguri	17-02-24
Aisha Hamman	16	Boko Haram <i>Amira</i> and <i>Rijalu'am</i>	Mubi	12-09-24
Aisha Ibrahim	18	Boko Haram <i>Amira Gazuwa</i>	Mubi	12-09-24
Baba Gas	46	Boko Haram senior commander <i>Kayt</i>	Mubi	13-09-24
Benedict Kruzen	44	Freelance journalist based in Maiduguri in the first decade of the conflicts; reported and provided support for diverse international media organizations, including the BBC	phone interview	22-04-23
Dogara Bitrus	37	Channels Television Reporter in Maiduguri	Maiduguri	01-02-23
Emperor Simon	39	Channels Television Reporter in Maiduguri	Abuja	22-01-23

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Fatima Suleiman	20	Boko Haram <i>Amiran Yaki</i>	Mubi	12-09-24
Fidelis Mbah	48	BBC/Al Jazeera Journalist	Abuja	26-04-23
Gambo Usman	26	Boko Haram <i>Amira</i> later became an <i>amaliyya</i>	Mubi	12-09-24
Ja'afar Lala	32	Boko Haram senior commander <i>Munzur</i>	Mubi	12-09-24
Junaid Bindawa	65	General Officer Commanding 7 th Division, Nigeria Army in Maiduguri Borno State	Kaduna	23-09-24
Lilian Unaegbu	42	Aid worker in Maiduguri, served with NGOs including Oxfam and UN Women	Abuja	03-10-23
Maryam Abdullahi	24	Boko Haram <i>Amira Mata</i>	Maiduguri	18-02-24
Maryam Isa	21	Lived in the <i>daulla</i> for 6 years	Maiduguri	18-02-24
Mayeni Jones	35	BBC Africa Correspondent	Lagos	15-01-23
Mike Omeri	60	Former Director of National Orientation Agency (NOA) between 2012-2016	Abuja	10-08-23
Samira Garba	25	Boko Haram <i>Amira Gazuwa</i>	Maiduguri	17-02-24
Sarkin Yaki Bello	67	Major General rtd. First coordinator Nigeria Counterinsurgency and Counterterrorism in the Office of the National Security Adviser (ONSA) from 2011-2014	Abuja	10-08-23
Yvonne Ndege	45	Al Jazeera Journalist	Phone interview	19-01-23

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